

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Approaches to Improve bioavailability and oral absorption of low water-soluble drug by self-emulsifying drug delivery system

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Abstract

Self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS), a type of lipid-based technology which are isotropic mixtures of oil, surfactant, solvent, and co-solvents generated by the activity of liquid or solid self-emulsifying ingredients onto powders. It shown interest in the recently for enhancement of solubility and bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs (BCS-II). With the novelty of research in this field, novel Excipients have been design with novel properties for enhances solubility, Bioavailability and oral absorption to achieving target response. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) emerged as an insightful approach for delivering highly hydrophobic entities to enhance their bioavailability. SEDDS increase drug bioavailability in addition to improving the solubility of poorly soluble drugs by a number of additional potential pathways, such as avoiding the hepatic first-pass effect, blocking P-gp efflux, and overcoming resistance to metabolism by the cytochrome P450 family of enzymes in the gut and liver. Conventional SEDDS were developed in a liquid form which owned numerous overcome like low stability and drug loading efficiency, fewer choices of dosage forms and irreversible precipitation of drug or excipients. To address these curbs solid-SEDDS (S-SEDDS) was introduced as an efficient strategy that combined advantages of solid dosage forms such as increased stability, portability and patient compliance along with substantial improvement in the bioavailability. This review highlights parts of SEDDS, and their characterization evaluation. Which are completely summarized via different techniques.

Keywords: Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS); Lipophilic drugs; lipids; Surfactant; Co-surfactant; Oral absorption; Oral bioavailability; Characterization and evaluation

1. Introduction

SEDDS is a Novel formulation employed to increase solubility and consequently the bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs such as BCS Class-II drug include Bilastine, Vitamin-E, monoxidil, posoconazole, etoricoxib, safinamide, eltrombopag olamine, brexpiprazole, ketoprofen, indomethacin and hydrocortisone. The BCS Class-II Drugs exhibit poor aqueous solubility, which affects their low bioavailability, variable absorption after oral delivery [1]. There are formulations strategies have been described to increase the dissolution rate of drugs by reducing their particle size (agitation, high energy approach) and salt formation, using excipient such as lipids surfactants, co-surfactant, and cyclodextrins for SEDDS based formulation. A relatively new approach for poorly soluble drugs is lipid-based formulations, particularly self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS). SEDDS are isotropic mixtures of oils and surfactants with or without co-surfactants, which act as lipid-based formulations after oral application in aqueous gastrointestinal fluid and upon gentle agitation can form an oil-in-water emulsion [1-3].

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Due to patient compliance and convenience of administration, oral route of administration is the most favored route of administration. Despite the significant benefits of this route, it frequently has low bioavailability either because to poor water solubility, permeability, or medication dissolution rate. A formulator faces a significant hurdle when creating a successful product: improving oral bioavailability [2]. Due to their weak water solubility, class II drugs under the biopharmaceutical classification system frequently have a low oral bioavailability. The development of lipid-based drug delivery systems has become a key formulation approaches to address difficulties with inadequate bioavailability out of the many options that are currently accessible [4].

Moreover, many novelty of technology have been developed to the impact of the self-emulsification process on the drug may result in a shift in droplet size distribution that varies with the drug's concentration. It is important to note that emulsions with smaller oil droplets in more complex preparations are more susceptible to alterations brought on by the addition of drugs substance. Pre-formulation solubility investigations are therefore significant for the creation of an appropriate SEEDS that applies significant shear stress [5,6]. Turbulence and hydrodynamics are two hypotheses that can account for droplet size. By using this technique, nano-emulsion with droplet sizes under 100 nm can be created (Table-1). The type of homogenizer, the makeup of the sample, and the working conditions of the homogenizer, including time, intensity, and temperature, all have a role in the generation of droplet size of nanoemulsion utilizing high pressure homogenizers. Nanoemulsion production frequently uses high pressure homogenization [1, 3, 6].

Table 1 Difference between SEDDS and SNEDDS

Property	SEDDS	SNEDDS
Mean globule size	>300 nm	< 100 nm
Appearance	Turbid	Optically clear
HLB value	< 12	< 12
Classification as per LFCS	Type II	Type IIIb
Concentration of oil	40–80%	> 20%
Concentration of surfactant	30–40%	40-80%

Figure 1 Mechanism of drug absorption from small intestine

SEDDS delivery system enhance the solubilization of active ingredients by creating a lipid Base emulsion and a concentration gradient that directs lipid loaded drug transport to the proper intestinal tissues absorption for site action. The performance of such a delivery system in vivo depends more on how it behaves in the gastrointestinal tract than

on its particle size. Lipid-based formulations provide effects that similar to the consumption of food [8]. The bile salt-lecithin-mixed micelles employed in the system solubilize the digested products of the lipids used in the system, which creates a fine colloidal dispersion that improves absorption [9,10]. For better understanding are shown in figure-1.

2. Significant role of Permeability glycoprotein (P-gp) in permeability, absorption and bioavailability of drug

The multidrug resistance gene (MDR) in humans produces the permeability glycoprotein (P-gp). It is the most widely distributed ATP-binding cassette (ABC) Tran membrane transporter ever discovered and the first [3]. Two homologous nucleotide binding domains and two homologous Tran's membrane domains make up the single polypeptide that makes up P-gp. For substrate binding and efflux, two Tran's membrane domains each made up of six Trans membrane helices combine to produce a single, broad, flexible channel. P-gp is linked to a series of dynamic conformational changes in the transporter, including dimerization of nucleotide binding domains, drug efflux, ATP hydrolysis, and restoration to the initial state. P-gp is expressed in the plasma membranes of the liver, kidney, bladder, blood-brain barrier cells, lungs, and, most importantly for oral drug administration, the esophagus, stomach, jejunum, and colon. P-gp transports molecules from inside cells to the extracellular space, preventing endogenous substances (including lipids, proteins, and metabolic products) and xenobiotics (like medications) from accumulating in cells [11-13]. As a result, P-gp affects absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion by pushing drug molecules back into the GI lumen, preventing them from entering organs like the brain, collaborating with cytochrome P450, and altering the function of the biliary and renal tubules, respectively [14].

3. Components of SEDDS

3.1. Drug substance

For the preparations of SEDDS Generally poorly water soluble drugs especially BCS-II Drugs (low solubility and high permeability) are used. It has lipophilic in nature with variable absorption pattern. BCS Class-II drug include Bilastine, vitamin E, monoxidil, posoconazole, etoricoxib, safinamide, eltrombopag olamine, brexpiprazole, etc [11, 14].

3.2. Lipids (Oil)

Table 2 Components of self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS)

Component	Role	Example
Lipid (oil)	Solubilization and GI transit Increase Intestinal permeability Protect drug from degradation Lymphatic transport and Reduce food effect Inter-intra subject variability	Oleic acid, Caster oil, capryol 90, ethyl oleate, labrafil and capmul PG-8NF, Crodamol oil, , peceol, rose oil,
Surfactant	Solubilization and emulsification Regulation the droplet size and release rate Inhibits of Pgp efflux CYP3A4, Help in opening of tight junction	Labrasol ALF, labraf IF, Tween 80, 20, 60, labrasol, span 80, 85, cremophore and kolliphore.
Co-surfactant	Solubilization and emulsification Help in dispersion and make flexibility to interface Reduce the amount of surfactant	Capryol, plurol oleique, Ethanol, isopropyl alcohol, 1-butanol, propylene glycol, transcutool HP
Drug	For the preparations of SEDDS Generally Poorly water soluble drugs Specially BCS-II Drugs are used.	BCS Class-II drug include Bilastine, vitamin E, monoxidil, posoconazole, etoricoxib, safinamide, eltrombopag olamine, brexpiprazole,

Oils are the most crucial excipients playing vital role in the SEDDS formulation to their ability to dissolve large amounts of lipophilic drugs. It improves transport through the lymphatic system. Moreover, lipidic parts cause secretion of bile and pancreatic juices resulting in the formation of mixed micelles comprising of bile salts, phospholipids and cholesterol [11, 15]. By virtue of such micelles formation, solubility of poorly soluble components is remarkably increased and increases the solubilization capacity of poorly soluble drugs in the GIT. Lipids exist in solid, semi-solid and liquid states and as described with examples in Triglycerides are commonly classified based on carbon chain length into short chain (SCT) composed of less than 5 carbon atoms, medium chain (MCT) consisting of 6–12 and long chain (LCT) consisting of 12–22 carbon atoms. Due to the short length of the carbon chain, MCTs directly diffuse through the gastrointestinal tract by the mechanism of passive diffusion into the portal system without undergo any molecular modifications. Lipids enable faster absorption from of the gastrointestinal tract compared to long-chain triglycerides and are preferred due to their greater capacity for drug dissolution and higher resistance to oxidation [16, 17]. Triglyceride vegetable oils are well absorbed and digested. Due to their safety profile resulting from their source of origin, are mostly preferred. They are a mixture of triglycerides from different chain lengths and saturation rates. But they find limited applications due to low content solubility of lipophilic drugs and poor self-dispersion properties (N) [18].

3.3. Surfactants

Surfactant is one of the essential components in the formulation, as they promote the emulsification properties (during the preparation of SEDDS, SEDDS able to lower the interfacial tension to a very small value which facilitates dispersion process). Surfactants, being amphiphilic in nature, can dissolve (or solubilize) relatively high amounts of hydrophobic drug compounds [12, 19]. The type and concentration of the surfactant showing effect on droplet size of micro- or nanoemulsion. Therefore, two significant factors that are hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value and concentration of the surfactants. The mostly utilized emulsifiers include Tween 80, 20, 60, labrasol, cremophore and kolliphore Sorbitan mono oleate (Span 80), Polyoxy-40-hydrogenated castor oil (Cremophor RH40), and Polyoxyethylated glycerides. In selection of a surfactant, safety is an important factor. Surfactants which are obtained from natural origin are more safety to use the Synthetic surfactants emulsifiers [20]. Moreover, these surfactants have a limited capacity for self-emulsification. Emulsifiers from natural sources are seldom employed for the formulation of SEDDS. Ionic surfactants are shown to be more harmful than non-ionic surfactants but may induce reversible improvements in intestinal lumen permeability. Normally, to form stable formulations, the surfactant concentration varies from 30-40% w/w for SEDDS [21,22].

3.4. Co-surfactant

Table 3 Structure and Chemical Constituent

S.n	Excipient structure	Chemical constituent	HLB value
1	 Oleic acid	Octaic-9-enoic acid or cis-9-octadecenoic acid	1-2
2	 Peceol	Glyceryl monooleate 40	1-2
3	 castor oil	Fatty acid and neutral lipids (triglycerides)	15

5	<p>Labrafil</p>	Oleoyl macrogol glycerides	4
6	<p>capryol 90</p>	Propylene glycol monocaprylate (type ii)	9-12
7	<p>Tween 20</p>	Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monolaurate	16-17
8	<p>Tween 60</p>	Polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate	14-15
	<p>Span 80</p>	Sorbitan monooleate	4-5
7	<p>Lauroglycol 90</p>	Propylene glycol mono- and di-esters of lauric acid (type ii)	4-5
9	<p>Capryol PGMC</p>	Propylene glycol monocaprylate (type i)	4-5
10	<p>Transcutol HP</p>	Diethylene glycol monoethyl ether	4-5

Whenever Low interfacial tension can sporadically be achieved with a single surfactant consequently, the addition of a co solvent or additional surfactant (co surfactant) is typically required. They can work together with surfactants to make the oil more soluble for the drug and more dispersible for the surfactant, making the nano-emulsion more stable and homogeneous [23]. By enhancing interfacial fluidity, the use of co surfactants or co solvents can lessen the surfactant's local irritancy and formulation dose variability. It has also been reported that the size distribution and the size of the

nano-emulsion area are significantly influenced by the weight ratio of the surfactant to the co surfactant or co solvent. Propylene glycol, ethanol, poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG), as well as more recent co solvents like Transcutol® HP, are all common co solvents. Co solvents, on the other hand, can improve drug solubilization in the formulation, but due to their polarity, their quantity should be kept to a minimum. Following aqueous dispersion, co solvents readily migrate toward the water phase, resulting in drug precipitation [1,3,24]. In addition, drug precipitation can occur when alcohols and other volatile co solvents evaporate into capsule shells. In addition to the components that have already been presented, additional components, such as antioxidants, viscosity enhancers, and components for modified drug release, may be utilized in the SEDDS and SNEDDS formulation are shown in table-2 [25].

4. Method of preparations of SEDDS

4.1. High pressure homogenizer

An homogenizer primarily comprises of a pump and a homogenizing valve from a technical perspective. For the preparation of nano-formulation The High pressure is required to fluid forced into the valve where the homogenization occurs using a pump. Fine emulsion is formed depending upon the application of high sheer stress. Turbulence and hydrodynamic are two theories that might be used to explain the droplet size. By using this technique, nano-emulsion with droplet sizes under 100 nm can be created [26]. The type of homogenizer, sample position, and operating settings of the homogenizer, such as time, intensity, and temperature, are all elements that affect the generation of droplet size of nanoemulsion utilizing high pressure homogenizers. The process of high pressure homogenization is frequently used to create nanoemulsion of components for food, medicine, and biotechnology [1,27].

4.2. High energy approach

The high energy technique, which results in the preparation of nanoemulsion by combining isotropic mixture of surfactants, oil, and co-solvent, calls for high mechanical energy. High energy techniques are used extensively during nanoemulsion formulation. High mechanical energies are utilized to break up big droplets into nanosized droplets, creating nanoemulsion with high kinetic energies. These form strong disruptive forces. Basically, SNEDDS rely on the phenomenon of self-emulsification and have low energy requirements [28,29].

4.3. Micro-fluidization

A device called a micro-fluidizer is necessary for the micro-fluidization process. The positive displacement pump forces the product towards the direction of the interaction chamber. A tiny droplet channel called a micro channel can be seen in this system. Following the formation of the product, it is transported by micro channels to the impingement area, where a nanoemulsion of incredibly small droplets is created. When the mixture of the aqueous phase and the oil phase is put to the homogenizer, a coarse emulsion is then created. The formation of a transparent and uniformly stable nanoemulsion results from additional processing [3,28,30].

4.4. Sonication method

Sonication method Sonication is one of the useful techniques for forming SNEDDS. Compared to other high-energy methods, ultra-sonication is superior in terms of cleaning and operation. The cavitations forces generated by ultrasonic waves break down macro emulsions into nanoemulsion during ultrasonic emulsifications. The emulsion shrinks to the size of Nanoparticles as a result of this process. The reduction in droplet size is caused by the sonication mechanism [3,29,31].

5. Material and methods

5.1. Materials

Pure drug API used in the study were purchased from different pharmaceutical/ chemical industrial/research laboratory [8,32]. The solvents and excipient were used for analytical calibration curve and preparation of SEDDS purchased from following pharmaceutical/ chemical industrial/research laboratory which are mention in below Table-4.

Table 4 Different drug substance and analytical grade Material

Material				Ref. no
Chemical	Supplier laboratory	Solvent	Supplier laboratory	
Chlorpromazine	Global Pharmaceutical Pvt. Ltd. Islamabad, Pakistan	Methanol	Sigma-Aldrich (Munich, Germany)	[8]
Ceftriaxone sodium	Avonchem, New Hampshire, UK) United Kingdom	Analytical grade	Sigma-Aldrich (Munich, Germany)	[18]
Resveratrol	Xian Lukee Bio-Tech Co., Ltd., (Xi'an, Shaanxi Sheng, People's Republic of China)	Analytical grade	Loba Chemie, Mumbai, India	
Itraconazol	Matrix Laboratories Ltd. (Hyderabad, India)	Analytical grade	Spectrochem (Mumbai, India).	[19]

5.2. Methods

5.2.1. Solubility studies

The solubility of gifted pure drug sample was determined in various natural oils (cotton seed oil, sunflower seed oil, and soybean oil), synthetic/semi synthetic oils (Capmul MCM EP, Labrafil 1944 CS, Labrail M2125 CS, Labrafil M2130 CS, ethyl oleate), and surfactants/co surfactants (Tween 20, Tween 80, PEG 400, Labrasol, Solutol HS 15, Carbitol, and Span 80). Adequate amounts of pure drug sample were added to 1 ml of each oil/surfactant and vortexed until completely dispersed (around 10 mins) [6, 32]. Then, the mixtures were kept in a isothermal shaking at 50 rpm and 37 ± 0.5 °C for 24 h, followed by homogenate centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 min or 5000rpm for 5 min. The supernatants were collected and filtered through a 0.45 μ m syringe filter and Dilute in mixed solvent system (dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and Acetonitrile (ACN) (50:50, v/v)). The filtrates were assayed by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer or high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with a detector [30,33].

5.2.2. Selection of Surfactant and co surfactant:

According to the previously described procedure, the selection of surfactant was based on its emulsifying property. The number of inversions necessary to emulsify the lipid phase in water was examined to assess the emulsification capability of surfactants. Chosen oil (300 mg) was combined with an equal amount of different surfactants, and then heated to between 45 and 50 °C. Following the addition of the mixture to 30 ml of distilled water, the number of inversions necessary to emulsify the oil in aqueous medium was counted [34]. The resulting mixture may be left out for two hours, and a UV-vis spectrophotometer was used to measure the % transmittance at λ_{max} nm while using distilled water as a control [35,36].

Furthermore, the selection of co-surfactant was made based on how well it would improve the surfactant's capacity for emulsification. The appropriate co-surfactant was chosen using a turbidimetric approach from a variety of co-surfactants. In order to achieve a chosen surfactant was combined in a 2:1 ratio with several co-surfactants, resulting in a mixture known as "S-mix." Oil was added to the S-mix in a 1:1 ratio after the mixtures were heated at 45–50 °C to homogenize the contents. Each resulting mixture (300 mg) might produce nano-emulsions by emulsifying with 30 ml of distilled water. Transparent nano-emulsions were tested for relative turbidity, let to stand for 2 hours, and then their percent transmittance was measured in accordance with the guidelines for surfactant screening [37,38].

5.2.3. Construction of Pseudo-Ternary Phase Diagrams

The ternary phase diagram was built using olive oil, Tween 80 (a surfactant), and propylene glycol (a co surfactant), which were chosen based on the findings of the saturation solubility investigations. In order to create a variety of formulations, different oil concentrations (10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%) were used [29]. Different weight ratios of surfactant and co surfactant (Smix) were combined at each oil percentage (1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4, respectively). By combining the specified weight of each component in small glass vials, and then vortex mixing the mixture until a clear solution was obtained, these Smix ratios were chosen in increasing concentration of surfactant with respect to co surfactant and vice versa formulation were obtained and prepared. Up until usage, the mixes were kept at room temperature [29,39]. Visual analysis was used to examine the self-emulsifying abilities of SEDDS formulations. A magnetic stir bar was used to gently combine the contents of each formulation after an exact measured 0.2 ml of each formulation was added to 100 ml of water in a glass beaker at 37°C. On the basis of the emulsion's

apparent stability, clarity, and speed of emulsification, various formulations were grouped. The formulations were then given a "good" or "bad" rating depending on how easily the oil droplets dispersed in the water without further coalescence within a minute of addition and produced a clear emulsion with a bluish tint or if there was little to no emulsion formation and the oil droplets immediately coalesced. Phase diagram was constructed by identifying the good self-emulsifying region using custom design software [40]. The Common SEDDS formulation available in market, excipient used and their outcome are shown in table-5.

Table 5 Common SEDDS formulation, excipient and their outcome

Drug substance	Excipient	Outcome	Ref. No.
Chlorpromazine	Oil (captex, triacetin, linseed oil, and olive oil), surfactants (Tween 85), and ethanol.	1.5-fold increased elimination half-life ($p < 0.01$), up to 6-fold increased oral bioavailability, and 1.7-fold decreased plasma clearance rate ($p < 0.01$) compared to a drug suspension.	[8]
Clofazimine	Oils: olive oil Surfactants: Tween 80, co-surfactants (peg 400, peg 200, peg 600, span 60)	Clofazimine delivery could not be directly related to droplet size, size distribution and zeta-potential; where a reduced droplet size and increased zeta-potential normally meaningfully enhance rapid and increased drug permeation during dermal drug delivery	[18]
Itraconazole	Capryol 90, Labrasol, Tween 20 and Transcutol P	Ratios of oil's/CoS mixture in an attempt to increase its release rate and bioavailability.	[19]
Calcimimetic Cinacalcet HCl	Oil: peceol, capmul mcm, labrafac w11349, triacetin, labrafac pg, captex 200p and captex 355 Surfactant: labrasol, kolliphor rh40, tween 80 and tween20 Co-solvent: lauroglycol 90, pleurol olique cc 497cg, peg 300, peg 400	Better dissolution profile with nearly 2.5 times cumulative % drug release than the pure drug in 30 min. In vivo studies showed threefold augmentations in oral bioavailability with increased Cmax and decreased Tmax for optimized formulation in comparison with aqueous suspension of pure drug	[36]
Rosuvastatin calcium	Oil: olive oil and cinnamon oil, (oleoyl polyoxyl-6 glycerides), labrafac® lipophile wl 1349 (caprylic capric triglyceride), labrasol® (caprylocaproyl macrogol-8 glycerides), peceol® (glyceryl monooleate), Tween® 80 (polysorbate 80) and hydrochloric acid	Overcome its poor solubility, and augment its anticancer activity) % transmittance: $99.05 \pm 0.09\%$ and highest drug solubility: 80.52 ± 2.57 mg/ml, globule size of 17.53 ± 0.89 nm, a zeta potential of -10.2 ± 0.21 mv, and a cloud point of 88.5 ± 0.54 °c	[37]
Senicapoc (potent antisickling agent)	Oil: capryol pgmc®, castor oil Surfactants: cremophor-el® and Tween® 80 Co-surfactants (transcutol hp® and peg 400) Surfactant: co surfactant in a 2:1 (w/w) ratio).	Investigations showed the potential of SNEDDSs to enhance the solubility and permeation of insoluble drugs such as SEN, although further preclinical studies are required before clinical trials can be conducted.	[40]
Ceftriaxone sodium (lower permeability and gastric instability)	Oil: cinnamon oil (43.33% w/w), soya bean oil, nutmeg oil, coconut oil, cinnamon oil, Surfactant: Tween 80 (30% w/w)	it was not be delivered orally due to its lower permeabilityso SNEDD formulation efficiently permeated across cell membrane and increase the drug oral bioavailability in animals	[42]

	Co-surfactant: propylene glycol (26.77% w/w), polyethylene glycol 400, polyethylene glycol 200 (peg 200)		
Curcumin (improved anti-cancer activity)	Tween 80, peg 200 and cinnamon oil were selected as surfactant (30%), co-surfactant (30%), and oil (40%).	Efficiently enhance CMN bioavailability, prevent its pre-mature metabolism and increase its intracellular delivery, Absorption and anticancer activity was high.	[44]
Candesartan (loaded self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery)	Oil: capmul Surfactant: pg-8 Co- solvent: kolliphor el	In vitro drug release study indicated up to 1.99- and 1.10-fold enhancement in dissolution rate from SNEDDS	[45]
Fexofenadine	Maisine 35-1 (monoglyceride/ diglyceride mixture) and Labrasol (HLB = 14) Propylene Glycol Dicaprylocaprate), and Capmul	Bioenhancer excipients were promising strategies for enhancing dissolution rate and thereby oral bioavailability of the fexofenadine	[49]

5.3. Preparation solid SEDDS

The formulations were prepared by dissolving a quantity of drug substance in the mixture of oil, surfactant and co-surfactant, at 40 °C in a water bath. This mixture was mixed by vertaxing until a transparent preparation was obtained. The formulation was equilibrated at ambient temperature for at least 48 hours to examine for any sign of turbidity or phase separation [29, 32]. The General Method of Preparation Solid SEDDS are shown in figure-2.

Figure 2 General Method of Preparation Solid SEDDS

5.4. Evaluation of SEDDS

Table 6 Common parameter and techniques used for SEDDS Characterization

S.N	Parameter	Evaluation of SEDDS Using following Techniques
Physicochemical Characterization		
1.	Droplet Size and Zeta Potential Analysis	Dynamic light scattering (DLS)
2.	Solid state characterization	Differential scanning Calorimetry (DSC), X-ray diffractometer
3.	Morphological characterization	Scanning electron microscopy
In vitro evaluation		

4.	<i>In-vitro</i> studies	Dissolution apparatus
5.	<i>In vitro</i> permeation studies	Parallel artificial membrane permeability assay
6.	<i>In- vitro</i> lipolysis	pH stat model
7.	In-vivo pharmacokinetic study	<i>In-vivo</i> evaluation
8.	Clinical trials in Humans	Pharmacokinetic, bioequivalence toxicity, pharmacodynamic

Evaluation of the final SEDDS for various criteria is always significant. The following is a summary of the common parameter and techniques used for SEDDS characterization in Table-6 [2,33,50]:

5.4.1. Drug content

The required quantity of SEDDS formulation was taken and diluted in methanol. Volume was made up to 25 ml with methanol (1 mg/ml). 0.1 ml (100 ug) was withdrawn from the above solution and diluted up to 10 ml with methanol (10 ug/ml). Aliquots of 40ppm were injected into HPLC system, to analyze at given λ_{max} [3,51].

5.4.2. Visual Assessment

Self-emulsification assessment is aided by visual observation. After water dilution of SEDDS, the presence of a clear, isotropic, transparent solution supports Microemulsion creation, but an opaque, milky white appearance shows macro emulsion evolution. Lack of precipitation and/or phase separation indicates the stability of the formulation [52].

5.4.3. Investigation of droplet size

The kind and concentration of the surfactant determine the size of the droplet. Optimal drug release, in vivo absorption, and stability depend on the micro emulsion's narrow droplet size distribution, which is created when SMEDDS is diluted with water. DLS techniques are used for droplet size analysis [53,54].

5.4.4. Determination Zeta Potential

Zeta potential determines the surface charge of the produced droplets in the dispersion liquid and informs the stability of the droplets. The electrophoretic mobility of the droplets is measured to find out. Although in the case of SEDDS, zeta potential is not more critical for evaluating the stability of the emulsion; the charge on the droplet plays a crucial role in enhancing drug absorption. This occurs because positively charged droplets interact with the negatively charged membrane in an efficient manner [55-57].

5.4.5. Time Required For Emulsification

The oil/surfactant and oil phase ratios influence how long it takes to emulsify a mixture [58]. This is determined using a basket dissolution apparatus, which monitors the generation of a clear solution as it is being stirred after formulation is added drop by drop to a water-filled basket.

5.4.6. Determination of cloud point

The temperature at which a homogeneous solution loses its transparency is known as the cloud point. The surfactant typically loses its capacity to produce micelles above the cloud point. It is discovered by gradually increasing the formulation's temperature and monitoring the turbidity spectrophotometrically [33,58]. The temperature at which the % transmittance starts to decline is known as the surfactant's cloud point. The cloud point of formulations should be greater than 37.5°C to preserve self-emulsification [59].

5.4.7. Viscosity measurement

The required quantity of SEDDS was weighed and transferred to beaker and the viscosity of formulation was determined with the help of Brookfield Viscometer at 10 rpm for 5 min and the corresponding dial reading on the viscometer was noted [29, 60].

5.4.8. Liquefaction time

This analysis is done to find out how long Solid SEDDS take to melt in a GI environment that is simulative without moving. Transparent polyethylene film is used to cover the dose form, which is attached via thread to a thermometer's

bulb. After that, the thermometer should be kept at 37°C while being submerged in a round-bottomed flask filled with 250 mL of simulated stomach juice devoid of pepsin. The time it takes for the liquefaction to occur is then recorded [30,61].

5.4.9. Test of thermodynamic stability

The Performance of a formulation depends on physical stability since chemical precipitation in the excipient matrix could be harmful. Excipient separation can be caused by poor formulation physical stability, decreased bioavailability, and diminished therapeutic efficacy [62]. When the formulation and the gelatin shell of the capsule are incompatible, brittleness, softness, and delayed or partial medication release may result. These studies are conducted using the ensuing cycles [63].

5.4.10. Test for Transmittance

Transmittance is a quantifiable feature that can be used to calculate self-emulsification time and droplet size. A turbidity meter is used to measure the turbidity after a certain amount of SEDDS has been added to a set amount of acceptable medium while it has been continuously stirred at 50 rpm on a magnetic stirrer at the right temperature [47,64]. The rate of turbidity shift, or rate of emulsification, cannot be measured because the amount of time needed for full emulsification is too short. Following emulsification, the growth of droplets is monitored by turbidimetric analysis.

5.4.11. Dissolution Studies

Dissolution studies of SEDDS was carried out using USP Dissolution apparatus I (basket type) at speed of 50 rpm in 900 mL 0.1 N HCl at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. In the experiment, one marketed capsule (100 mg) and four SEDDS filled were used for the dissolution studies. Aliquots of 5 mL were removed at 2, 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75 and 120 min. Volume of aliquots was replaced with fresh dialyzing medium each time [65]. These samples were analyzed quantitatively for amount of Drug released at corresponding time by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-18000, at given λ_{max} [12,30,66].

5.4.12. Release kinetics

To study the release kinetics, in vitro dissolution study was fitted in various data obtained from kinetic models: Zero order as cumulative percent of drug released versus time, first order as log cumulative percentage of drug remaining versus time and Higuchi's model as cumulative percent drug released versus square root of time, Hixon Crowell describes the release from systems when there is a change in a surface area and diameter of particles respectively [12, 23]. To determine the mechanism of drug release, the data was fitted into Korsmeyer and Peppas equation as log cumulative percentage of drug released versus log time and the exponent n was calculated from slope of the straight line. For slab matrix, if exponent is 0.5, then diffusion mechanism is Fickian; if $0.5 < n < 1.0$, then it is anomalous transport. If n is 1.0, it is case II transport and if $n > 1.0$, then it is super case II transport [44,51,66].

6. Conclusion

After review of various self-emulsifying drug delivery system, SEDDS formulations increase solubility and consequently the bioavailability of poorly water soluble drugs, which allow better formulation versatility and characterization of lipidic excipients, offer a viable alternative to serve the desired purpose through physicochemical and physiological mechanisms controlling drug absorption. SEDDS increase drug bioavailability in addition to improving the solubility of poorly soluble drugs by a number of additional potential pathways, such as avoiding the hepatic first-pass effect, blocking P-gp efflux, and overcoming resistance to metabolism by the cytochrome P450 family of enzymes in the gut and liver.

SEDDS's tiny globule size and surface activity make it possible for drugs to pass through the intestinal boundary layer and absorptive brush border membranes more effectively, ultimately leading to a faster start and longer duration of therapeutic action. The heterogeneity in bioavailability is additionally decreased by SEDDS' reduced vulnerability to gastric emptying delays and GI tract lipolysis, as well as by their high thermodynamic stability and resistance to dilution, which keeps the drug in a solubilized state during the absorption phase.

The authors of this review paper study make an effort to give a comprehensive overview of all the component, method of preparation, and significant characterization and evaluation features of these self-emulsifying formulations. Its anticipate that this will give us the motivation we need scientists working on product development, enabling future development of the SEDDS research product.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Authors' contributions

Authors read and agreed with the final manuscript.

References

- [1] Salawi A. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: a novel approach to deliver drugs. *Drug Delivery*. 2022 Dec 31;29(1):1811-23.
- [2] Rahman MA, Hussain A, Hussain MS, Mirza MA, Iqbal Z. Role of excipients in successful development of self-emulsifying/microemulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS/SMEDDS). *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. 2013 Jan 1;39(1):1-9.
- [3] Maji I, Mahajan S, Sriram A, Medtiya P, Vasave R, Khatri DK, Kumar R, Singh SB, Madan J, Singh PK. Solid self emulsifying drug delivery system: Superior mode for oral delivery of hydrophobic cargos. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2021 Sep 10;337:646-60.
- [4] Yeom DW, Song YS, Kim SR, Lee SG, Kang MH, Lee S, Choi YW. Development and optimization of a self-microemulsifying drug delivery system for atorvastatin calcium by using D-optimal mixture design. *International Journal of nanomedicine*. 2015;10:3865.
- [5] Na YG, Byeon JJ, Wang M, Huh HW, Son GH, Jeon SH, Bang KH, Kim SJ, Lee HJ, Lee HK, Cho CW. Strategic approach to developing a self-microemulsifying drug delivery system to enhance antiplatelet activity and bioavailability of ticagrelor. *International journal of nanomedicine*. 2019;14:1193.
- [6] Rani ER, Radha GV. Insights into novel excipients of self-emulsifying drug delivery systems and their significance: an updated review. *Critical Reviews™ in Therapeutic Drug Carrier Systems*. 2021;38(2).
- [7] Kohli K, Chopra S, Dhar D, Arora S, Khar RK. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: an approach to enhance oral bioavailability. *Drug discovery today*. 2010 Nov 1;15(21-22):958-65.
- [8] Baloch J, Sohail MF, Sarwar HS, Kiani MH, Khan GM, Jahan S, Rafay M, Chaudhry MT, Yasinzai M, Shahnaz G. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) for improved oral bioavailability of chlorpromazine: in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *Medicina*. 2019 May 24;55(5):210.
- [9] Patel J, Kevin G, Patel A, Raval M, Sheth N. Design and development of a self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system for telmisartan for oral drug delivery. *International journal of pharmaceutical investigation*. 2011 Apr;1(2):112.
- [10] Kumar R, Khursheed R, Kumar R, Awasthi A, Sharma N, Khurana S, Kapoor B, Khurana N, Singh SK, Gowthamarajan K, Wadhwani A. Self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system of fisetin: Formulation, optimization, characterization and cytotoxicity assessment. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2019 Dec 1;54:101252.
- [11] Kang BK, Lee JS, Chon SK, Jeong SY, Yuk SH, Khang G, Lee HB, Cho SH. Development of self-microemulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) for oral bioavailability enhancement of simvastatin in beagle dogs. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*. 2004 Apr 15;274(1-2):65-73.
- [12] Jaiswal P, Aggarwal G, Harikumar SL, Singh K. Development of self-microemulsifying drug delivery system and solid-self-microemulsifying drug delivery system of telmisartan. *International journal of pharmaceutical investigation*. 2014 Oct;4(4):195.
- [13] Kamboj S, Rana V. Quality-by-design based development of a self-microemulsifying drug delivery system to reduce the effect of food on Nelfinavir mesylate. *International journal of pharmaceuticals*. 2016 Mar 30;501(1-2):311-25.

- [14] Kanwal T, Saifullah S, ur Rehman J, Kawish M, Razzak A, Maharjan R, Imran M, Ali I, Roome T, Simjee SU, Shah MR. Design of absorption enhancer containing self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) for curcumin improved anti-cancer activity and oral bioavailability. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*. 2021 Feb 15;324:114774.
- [15] Mishra V, Nayak P, Yadav N, Singh M, Tambuwala MM, Aljabali AA. Orally administered self-emulsifying drug delivery system in disease management: advancement and patents. *Expert Opinion on Drug Delivery*. 2021 Mar 4;18(3):315-32.
- [16] Czajkowska-Kośnik A, Szekalska M, Amelian A, Szymańska E, Winnicka K. Development and evaluation of liquid and solid self-emulsifying drug delivery systems for atorvastatin. *Molecules*. 2015 Nov 25;20(12):21010-22.
- [17] Wang L, Yan W, Tian Y, Xue H, Tang J, Zhang L. Self-microemulsifying drug delivery system of phillygenin: formulation development, characterization and pharmacokinetic evaluation. *Pharmaceutics*. 2020 Feb 3;12(2):130.
- [18] Van Staden D, Du Plessis J, Viljoen J. Development of a self-emulsifying drug delivery system for optimized topical delivery of clofazimine. *Pharmaceutics*. 2020 Jun;12(6):523.
- [19] Chudasama A, Shah B, Patel V, Nivsarkar M, Vasu K, Shishoo C. Development of self emulsifying drug delivery system of itraconazole for oral delivery: formulation and pharmacokinetic consideration. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2015 Jun;45(3):271-83.
- [20] Dokania S, Joshi AK. Self-microemulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS)–challenges and road ahead. *Drug delivery*. 2015 Aug 18;22(6):675-90.
- [21] Shah AV, Desai HH, Thool P, Dalrymple D, Serajuddin AT. Development of self-microemulsifying drug delivery system for oral delivery of poorly water-soluble nutraceuticals. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2018 Jun 3;44(6):895-901.
- [22] Valicherla GR, Dave KM, Syed AA, Riyazuddin M, Gupta AP, Singh A, Mitra K, Datta D, Gayen JR. Formulation optimization of Docetaxel loaded self-emulsifying drug delivery system to enhance bioavailability and anti-tumor activity. *Scientific reports*. 2016 May 31;6(1):1-1.
- [23] Vohra AM, Patel CV, Kumar P, Thakkar HP. Development of dual drug loaded solid self microemulsifying drug delivery system: Exploring interfacial interactions using QbD coupled risk based approach. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*. 2017 Sep 1;242:1156-68.
- [24] Sahoo SK, Suresh PA, Acharya US. Design and development of self-microemulsifying drug delivery systems (SMEDDS) of telmisartan for enhancement of in vitro dissolution and oral bioavailability in rabbit. *Int J Appl Pharm*. 2018;10(4):117-26.
- [25] Zupančič O, Grießinger JA, Rohrer J, de Sousa IP, Danninger L, Partenhauser A, Sündermann NE, Laffleur F, Bernkop-Schnürch A. Development, in vitro and in vivo evaluation of a self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS) for oral enoxaparin administration. *European journal of pharmaceutics and biopharmaceutics*. 2016 Dec 1;109:113-21.
- [26] Gao H, Jia H, Dong J, Yang X, Li H, Ouyang D. Integrated in silico formulation design of self-emulsifying drug delivery systems. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*. 2021 Nov 1;11(11):3585-94.
- [27] Köllner S, Nardin I, Markt R, Griesser J, Prüfert F, Bernkop-Schnürch A. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: Design of a novel vaginal delivery system for curcumin. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*. 2017 Jun 1;115:268-75.
- [28] Visetvichaporn V, Kim KH, Jung K, Cho YS, Kim DD. Formulation of self-microemulsifying drug delivery system (SMEDDS) by D-optimal mixture design to enhance the oral bioavailability of a new cathepsin K inhibitor (HL235). *International journal of pharmaceutics*. 2020 Jan 5;573:118772.
- [29] Dae-Duk K, Voradanu V. Formulation of Self-Microemulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS) by D-optimal Mixture Design for Enhancing Oral Bioavailability of DN200428 (Cathepsin K Inhibitor) (Doctoral dissertation)
- [30] Komesli Y, Ozkaya AB, Ergur BU, Kirilmaz L, Karasulu E. Design and development of a self-microemulsifying drug delivery system of olmesartan medoxomil for enhanced bioavailability. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. 2019 May 17.
- [31] Arshad R, Tabish TA, Naseem AA, ul Hassan MR, Hussain I, Hussain SS, Shahnaz G. Development of poly-L-lysine multi-functionalized muco-penetrating self-emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS) for improved

solubilization and targeted delivery of ciprofloxacin against intracellular *Salmonella typhi*. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*. 2021 Jul 1;333:115972.

- [32] Balata GF, Essa EA, Shamardl HA, Zaidan SH, Abourehab MA. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems as a tool to improve solubility and bioavailability of resveratrol. *Drug design, development and therapy*. 2016;10:117.
- [33] Arshad R, Tabish TA, Kiani MH, Ibrahim IM, Shahnaz G, Rahdar A, Kang M, Pandey S. A hyaluronic acid functionalized self-nano-emulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) for enhancement in ciprofloxacin targeted delivery against intracellular infection. *Nanomaterials*. 2021 May;11(5):1086.
- [34] Buya AB, Beloqui A, Memvanga PB, Preat V. Self-nano-emulsifying drug-delivery systems: From the development to the current applications and challenges in oral drug delivery. *Pharmaceutics*. 2020 Dec 9;12(12):1194.
- [35] Buddhadev SS, Garala KC. Self-Nano Emulsifying Drug-Delivery Systems: From the Development to The Current Applications and Update of the Biopharmaceutical Aspect.(2021) Dec 26;13(6):112
- [36] Panigrahi KC, Patra C, Rao ME. Quality by design enabled development of oral self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system of a novel calcimimetic cinacalcet HCl using a porous carrier: in vitro and in vivo characterisation. *AAPS PharmSciTech*. 2019 Jul;20(5):1-7.
- [37] Sweed NM, Fayez AM, El-Emam SZ, Dawoud MH. Response surface optimization of self nano-emulsifying drug delivery system of rosuvastatin calcium for hepatocellular carcinoma. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2021 Jan;51(1):85-101.
- [38] Maji I, Mahajan S, Sriram A, Medtiya P, Vasave R, Khatri DK, Kumar R, Singh SB, Madan J, Singh PK. Solid self emulsifying drug delivery system: Superior mode for oral delivery of hydrophobic cargos. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2021 Sep 10;337:646-60.
- [39] Syukri Y, Martien R, Lukitaningsih E, Nugroho AE. Novel Self-Nano Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SNEDDS) of andrographolide isolated from *Andrographis paniculata* Nees: characterization, in-vitro and in-vivo assessment. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2018 Oct 1;47:514-20.
- [40] Buya AB, Ucakar B, Beloqui A, Memvanga PB, Preat V. Design and evaluation of self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery systems (SNEDDSs) for senicapoc. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 2020 Apr 30;580:119180.
- [41] Giddam R, Hepsiba S, Mukeri I. Formulation of Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System of Dolutegravir sodium. 2022 Nov 13;1-9
- [42] Kanwal T, Kawish M, Maharjan R, Ghaffar I, Ali HS, Imran M, Perveen S, Saifullah S, Simjee SU, Shah MR. Design and development of permeation enhancer containing self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS) for ceftriaxone sodium improved oral pharmacokinetics. *Journal of Molecular liquids*. 2019 Sep 1;289:111098.
- [43] Buya AB, Terrasi R, Mbinze JK, Muccioli GG, Beloqui A, Memvanga PB, Preat V. Quality-by-design-based development of a voxelator self-nanoemulsifying drug-delivery system with improved biopharmaceutical attributes. *Pharmaceutics*. 2021 Sep 2;13(9):1388.
- [44] Shukla M, Jaiswal S, Sharma A, Srivastava PK, Arya A, Dwivedi AK, Lal J. A combination of complexation and self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system for enhancing oral bioavailability and anticancer efficacy of curcumin. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2017 May 4;43(5):847-61.
- [45] Verma R, Kaushik D. Design and optimization of candesartan loaded self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system for improving its dissolution rate and pharmacodynamic potential. *Drug Delivery*. 2020 Jan 1;27(1):756-71.
- [46] Gardouh AR, Nasef AM, Mostafa Y, Gad S. Design and evaluation of combined atorvastatin and ezetimibe optimized self-nano emulsifying drug delivery system. *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 2020 Dec 1;60:102093.
- [47] Mohamad SA, Safwat MA, Elrehany M, Maher SA, Badawi AM, Mansour HF. A novel nasal co-loaded loratadine and sulphuride nanoemulsion with improved downregulation of TNF- α , TGF- β and IL-1 in rabbit models of ovalbumin-induced allergic rhinitis. *Drug delivery*. 2021 Jan 1;28(1):229-39.
- [48] Amado JR, Prada AL, Duarte JL, Keita H, da Silva HR, Ferreira AM, Sosa EH, Carvalho JC. Development, stability and in vitro delivery profile of new loratadine-loaded nanoparticles. *Saudi pharmaceutical journal*. 2017 Dec 1;25(8):1158-68.
- [49] Trivedi K, Patel PV, Pujara Z. Development and characterization of liquid and solid self-emulsifying drug delivery system of fexofenadine. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation*. 2013 Oct;43(5):385-94.

- [50] AboulFotouh K, Allam AA, El-Badry M, El-Sayed AM. Self-emulsifying drug-delivery systems modulate P-glycoprotein activity: Role of excipients and formulation aspects. *Nanomedicine*. 2018 Aug 3;13(14):1813-34.
- [51] Ahmad J, Kohli K, Mir SR, Amin S. Formulation of self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system for telmisartan with improved dissolution and oral bioavailability. *Journal of Dispersion Science and Technology*. 2011 Jul 1;32(7):958-68.
- [52] Murad H, Ahmed O, Ghabrah T, Gari M. Telmisartan self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system, compared with standard telmisartan, more effectively improves hepatic fibrosis in rats. *Dose-Response*. 2020 Dec 16;18(4):1559325820982190.
- [53] Nazari-Vanani R, Moezi L, Heli H. In vivo evaluation of a self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system for curcumin. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*. 2017 Apr 1;88:715-20.
- [54] Kadian R, Nanda A. A Comprehensive Insight on Recent Advancements in Self-emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems. *Current Drug Delivery*. 2023.
- [55] Dening TJ, Rao S, Thomas N, Prestidge CA. Novel nanostructured solid materials for modulating oral drug delivery from solid-state lipid-based drug delivery systems. *The AAPS journal*. 2016 Jan;18(1):23-40.
- [56] Zizzari AT, Pliatsika D, Gall FM, Fischer T, Riedl R. New perspectives in oral peptide delivery. *Drug discovery today*. 2021 Apr 1;26(4):1097-105.
- [57] Akiladevi DN. Formulation And Development Of Self Emulsifying Drug Delivery System For Few Drugs. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2017 Jan;8(0975-1491):1-33.
- [58] Bhagwat DA, Souza JI. Formulation and evaluation of solid self micro emulsifying drug delivery system using aerosil 200 as solid carrier. *International current pharmaceutical journal*. 2012 Nov 1;1(12):414-9.
- [59] Limbani MD, Patel LD. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SELF-NANO EMULSIFYING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS (SNEDDS) OF POORLY WATER SOLUBLE ANTILIPIDEMIC DRUGS. 2011 Nov;1443-11
- [60] Gursoy RN, Benita S. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDS) for improved oral delivery of lipophilic drugs. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy*. 2004 Apr 1;58(3):173-82.
- [61] Tang JL, Sun J, He ZG. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: strategy for improving oral delivery of poorly soluble drugs. *Current drug therapy*. 2007 Jan 1;2(1):85-93.
- [62] Karwal R, Garg T, Rath G, Markandeywar TS. Current trends in self-emulsifying drug delivery systems (SEDDSS) to enhance the bioavailability of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Critical Reviews™ in Therapeutic Drug Carrier Systems*. 2016;33(1).
- [63] Kumar A, Sharma S, Kamble R. Self emulsifying drug delivery system (SEDDS): Future aspects. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2010;2(4):7-13.
- [64] Uppulurj KB. Self nano emulsifying drug delivery systems for oral delivery of hydrophobic drugs. *Biomedical and pharmacology journal*. 2015 Apr 28;6(2):355-62.
- [65] Tang B, Cheng G, Gu JC, Xu CH. Development of solid self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: preparation techniques and dosage forms. *Drug discovery today*. 2008 Jul 1;13(13-14):606-12.
- [66] Zhang L, Zhang L, Zhang M, Pang Y, Li Z, Zhao A, Feng J. Self-emulsifying drug delivery system and the applications in herbal drugs. *Drug delivery*. 2015 May 19;22(4):475-86